

A Framework for Assessing Translational Validity in Analog-Based Research

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Abstract

Analog research—studies using surrogate organisms, simulated exposures, substitute environments, or proxy outcomes—underpins causal inference across fields. Yet no unified framework exists for determining when evidence from an analog validly informs conclusions about a target system. We show that substitutions along four dimensions—organism, setting, exposure, and outcome—threaten translational validity in distinct ways, and that the resulting study profile determines which causal claims a study can support independently of its design quality. The framework yields 16 possible profiles assessed against three Bradford Hill considerations (Analogy, Mechanism, Specificity), with inferential distance from the target quantified by Hamming distance. Substitutions along each dimension introduce different threats—confounding, altered causal pathways, or invalid proxy relationships—which we formalize using directed acyclic graphs. We demonstrate the framework with examples from human spaceflight analog research, showing how profile classification can either validate proxy outcomes or expose unsupported translational claims. The framework generalizes to any domain where analog evidence informs inference: rodent models in drug development, psychological paradigms, environmental health studies, and digital twins in engineering. When applied retrospectively, it identifies which studies in an evidence base can validly contribute to specific causal claims. When applied prospectively, it clarifies the evidentiary limitations inherent in a given analog design before resources are committed.

Introduction

Before astronauts fly long-duration missions, the risks are studied in ground-based analogs (1,2). Before environmental regulations are set, occupational cohorts serve as proxies for community exposures. Before a drug reaches human trials, it is tested in rodents. Yet only 5% of those drugs tested in animals reach regulatory approval for human use (3,4). Across medicine, toxicology, aerospace, and public health, critical decisions depend on evidence gathered from substitute systems—model organisms, simulated environments, proxy outcomes—because the target system cannot be studied directly. The question these decisions hinge on is always the same: do the findings translate?

This question has been addressed piecemeal within specific domains, but no unified framework exists for assessing translational validity across scientific disciplines. Each field develops its own heuristics, and the logic underlying those heuristics is rarely made explicit.

The problem becomes acute when analog evidence must be integrated into formal systems for evaluating causal claims. Ward et al. (5) describe a Level of Evidence framework developed for NASA human spaceflight risk management, built on modified Bradford Hill causal guidelines (6). Such systems require an upstream determination: which evidentiary criteria can a given study even address? A rodent study conducted in a terrestrial laboratory rarely speaks to *Specificity* in humans regardless of its sample size or design quality. A study which relies on a proxy outcome cannot establish that the actual outcome of interest occurs. Before asking how strong the evidence is, we must ask what it can be evidence for.

Here we address this question directly. We propose a four-dimension taxonomy for characterizing analog studies—organism, setting, exposure, and outcome—and show how substitutions along each dimension constrain which of Hill's causal guidelines a study can validly inform. The framework yields 16 possible study profiles, each with a distinct pattern of evidentiary utility. We detail the causal logic underlying each dimension's threats to translational validity, demonstrate the framework using examples from human spaceflight analog research, and

discuss generalization to other domains where analog evidence informs inference about systems that cannot be directly studied.

Analog Study Dimensions

Dimension 1: Organism

The organism aspect of a human analog study considers whether the study utilizes humans or a surrogate for humans. Here surrogates can take many forms, and which one is used typically depends most heavily on the scientific question to be answered. Possibilities include in vitro studies, insects, rodents, non-human primates, or any other non-human organism.

Dimension 2: Setting

The setting of an analog study refers to the context of the study, specifically whether data are produced in the actual environment of interest or a substitute one. Substitute settings include analog habitats, laboratories, and even observational studies in occupational settings. Substitute settings can also include one real-world location substituting for another, such as one factory being used to provide evidence of probable health effects for workers at another, similar facility.

Dimension 3: Exposure

Exposure refers to the specific environmental or situational factor that is under investigation as a cause of one or more specific outcomes. An analog may utilize the exact exposure (toxins, drugs, radiation, force vectors, etc.), or something that is only a simulation of that exposure.

Dimension 4: Outcome

The outcome is the specific result under study, believed to be caused by the exposure via the hypothesized causal mechanism. The outcome that an analog study observes can be either the actual outcome from the real-life situation or it can be a proxy outcome, such as a biomarker, precursor condition, sentinel event, etc.

The role of study design

A natural question is whether study design is a defining characteristic of an analog study. In this context we refer to study design in the broadest sense, referring to whether a study is observational or a controlled experiment, and within the latter category, aspects such as randomized or non-randomized exposures, blinded or non-blinded data evaluation, etc. Controlled, randomized experiments are held as the gold standard of high-quality/high-utility evidence primarily because they randomize exposure, and in so doing randomize unmeasured confounders, creating the conditions necessary for causal attribution and unbiased estimates of effect (7). However, these issues should be assessed separately, as it speaks to the quality of the evidence rather than its uses. We therefore view study design not as a fifth dimension of analog classification, but as a quality filter: poorly designed studies may be excluded regardless of their dimensional profile. Given adequate quality, evidentiary utility is determined by the four dimensions alone.

Analog Dimensions Drive Translational Validity

Each of the four dimensions can take one of two states: authentic (matching the target scenario) or analog (substituted). Since any combination of the 4 dimensions can be analog, this yields $2^4 = 16$ possible study profiles, ranging from fully authentic studies (all four dimensions match the target) to fully analog studies (all four dimensions substituted).

To quantify how far a given profile departs from the authentic case, we use the analog dimension Hamming distance—the number of dimensions in which the study differs from the

target scenario (8). A study using human subjects in the actual setting with the actual exposure but measuring a proxy outcome has a Hamming distance of 1. A study using surrogate organisms in a substitute setting with simulated exposure and proxy outcomes has a Hamming distance of 4.

Not all substitutions have equal consequences for what a study can tell us. We assess evidentiary utility by determining whether the data produced by the analog can fulfill three of the classic Bradford Hill causal considerations: Analogy to the real situation (plausibility), contribution to understanding causal pathways (mechanism), and support for specific exposure-outcome claims in humans (specificity). Of Hill's original nine guidelines, these three are properties that an individual study can satisfy. Temporality is a prerequisite for any causal claim. Consistency and Coherence describe agreement across multiple studies. Strength and Biological Gradient are correlates of causation rather than criteria for it. Experiment pertains to study design, which we assess separately. The remaining three criteria are therefore the appropriate targets for evaluating the evidentiary utility of a single analog study's profile.

Table 1 presents all 16 profiles with their Hamming distances and evidentiary utility ratings for the 3 considerations.

The Distance column uses a simple Hamming distance to score how different the profile is from the true scenario it seeks to simulate. The Hamming distance is, generally, the number of changes required to transform one string of values into another. Transforming the string "bat" to "cat" requires 1 change (changing b to c), and thus represents a Hamming distance of 1. Here the Hamming distance represents the number of dimensions in the profile that are analog rather than actual, with a range of possible scores of 0 to 4. Hamming distance in this application is a type of quantification of plausibility.

The entries in the cells under the evidentiary criteria columns describe whether or not each profile can meet each of the three Hill guidelines. The entries are coded as either Y, M, or N, for Yes, Maybe, and No. These codes signify whether an analog is assured to contribute (Y), is

Table 1. Fidelity profiles for analog studies with evidentiary utility and inferential distance from the true scenario.

Profile	Organism	Setting	Exposure	Outcome	Analogy	Mechanism	Specificity	Distance*
1	Human	Actual	Actual	Actual	Y	Y	Y	0
2	Human	Actual	Actual	Proxy	Y	Y	M	1
3	Human	Actual	Simulated	Actual	Y	M	M	1
4	Human	Substitute	Actual	Actual	Y	M	M	1
5	Human	Actual	Simulated	Proxy	Y	M	N	2
6	Human	Substitute	Actual	Proxy	Y	M	N	2
7	Human	Substitute	Simulated	Actual	Y	M	N	2
8	Human	Substitute	Simulated	Proxy	Y	M	N	3
9	Surrogate	Actual	Actual	Actual	Y	M	N	1
10	Surrogate	Actual	Actual	Proxy	Y	M	N	2
11	Surrogate	Actual	Simulated	Actual	Y	M	N	2
12	Surrogate	Substitute	Actual	Actual	Y	M	N	2
13	Surrogate	Actual	Simulated	Proxy	Y	M	N	3
14	Surrogate	Substitute	Actual	Proxy	Y	M	N	3
15	Surrogate	Substitute	Simulated	Actual	Y	M	N	3
16	Surrogate	Substitute	Simulated	Proxy	Y	N	N	4

* Distance is the Hamming distance from the real situation, defined as the number of characteristics one would need to change to transform the given scenario back into the real situation.

definitively unable to contribute (N), or may be able to contribute (M), depending on the circumstances. These contributions derive directly from the substitutions themselves, as detailed in the following section.

The Relationship Between Translational Validity and Evidentiary Utility

The Y/M/N ratings in Table 1 reflect the different threats to translational validity introduced by each type of substitution. All 16 profiles receive a 'Y' for Analogy because any analog study, regardless of its substitutions, can suggest that a causal relationship is worth investigating in the target system. Analogy is the lowest evidentiary bar: it provides plausibility and motivation for further inquiry, not confirmation. Even a study with maximum Hamming distance can generate hypotheses worth testing through higher-fidelity designs.

Specific substitutions within the four dimensions impose different limitations on what an analog study can contribute to our understanding of a causal system. Key concerns include the introduction of confounds, fundamental alterations to causal pathways, and the validity of proxy outcomes. Table 2 maps analog dimensions to these concerns, and the sub-sections that follow detail the causal logic underlying each.

As shown, some substitutions within the dimensions generate more serious limitations than others. The most fundamental limitation arises from the use of a surrogate organism, while the most difficult to assess or remediate is the substitution of setting. Concerns regarding simulated exposure are primarily mechanistic: although a simulated exposure is often chosen because it produces the desired outcome, it may do so through a different mechanistic pathway. Finally, proxy outcomes must be evaluated based on the divergence in causal mechanisms between the exposure and the proxy, as well as the relationship of the proxy to the actual outcome of interest. We explore these implications in more detail below.

Table 2. Ways in which substitutions in the dimensions of human analog studies threaten translational validity.

Dimension	Confounding	Alternate Causal Pathways	Outcome validity	Explanation and notes
Organism	X	X		Non-human organisms may have physiological differences and thus a different mechanism from that in humans (different DAG)
Setting	X			Changing settings potentially replaces one set of environmental confounders with another. This is the most difficult to assess.
Exposure		X		The simulated exposure may produce the outcome through a different mechanism (different DAG)
Outcome		X	X	A proxy outcome can have a different relationship with the exposure, and may not have an appropriate relationship with the true outcome.

Surrogate Organisms

The organism dimension is the most fundamental consideration when assessing translational validity. The key question is whether the causal pathways in the surrogate adequately reflect those in humans.

For treatment efficacy, the pathways demonstrated in humans should exist in the surrogate—otherwise the model cannot test whether the intervention works by the hypothesized mechanism. For harm assessment, the direction reverses: mechanisms of harm identified in the surrogate should be known to exist in humans—otherwise observed toxicity may not translate. In short, efficacy testing asks whether the surrogate can model a human hypothesis; harm assessment asks whether a surrogate finding could occur in humans.

It is also worth noting that even within a single study, not all findings are necessarily valid or invalid together. Mechanistic correspondence should be assessed for each exposure-outcome pairing separately, with targeted validation studies where pathway equivalence is uncertain.

A related consequence is differential confounding. Variables that covary with exposure or outcome in the surrogate may not do so in humans, meaning confounding structures identified in one species may not generalize to the other.

Substitute Settings

Table 2 shows that the concern when using substitute settings in analog studies is the potential change in the set of (often unknown and unmeasured) environmental variables induced by the change in setting. These variables may play one of several archetypal roles in the causal network: classical confounder, moderator, or mediator (Figure 1).

One obvious strategy for improving the evidentiary utility of analog studies that use substitute settings is to make substitute settings as close to the actual setting as possible, i.e. increase the “fidelity” of the setting. However, when trying to recreate actual conditions in the substitute setting investigators must: (1) realize that a particular environmental condition exists; (2) recognize that it may be related to the outcomes under study; (3) be able to measure it; and (4) be able to control it. That one or more of these conditions typically go unmet should be obvious to most researchers. Superficial fidelity—making the substitute setting look like the target—is not the same as mechanistic fidelity. The features easiest to replicate are often not the ones that matter causally.

Additionally, the measurement protocols required in substitute settings may themselves perturb the system under study. Instrumentation, sampling, and procedural requirements that enable data collection in the analog may introduce artifacts absent from the target environment.

As all substitute-setting analog studies will remove some unknown and unmeasured variables and introduce others, nearly all analog studies that use substitute settings are biased to an unknown extent. Thus, to treat evidence from a particular analog as valid for *Mechanism* and/or *Specificity*, investigators must be able to reasonably assume that any unknown setting-related exposures or conditions will have minimal effect on the outcomes under study. This assumes that any important potential confounders, moderators, or mediators have already been identified and accounted for in the study, and, therefore, any remaining unmeasured factors are unlikely to be consequential.

In cases where known factors of the true environment cannot be recreated in the substitute environment, the evidence produced by the analog may be considered best-case or worst-case, depending on the expected effect of the missing factor. In this way the analog can still be valid for *Mechanism* and potentially *Specificity*, with the understanding that any probability estimate it produces is a marginal estimate which establishes an upper or lower bound on risk and/or severity.

Simulated Exposure

Simulated exposures attempt to approximate exposures that are either difficult or expensive to experience, and are often used to obtain precise doses of exposure in experimental research. The primary limitation of simulated exposures is that they may have a different causal mechanism than the actual exposure, even if the simulated exposure superficially produces the same outcomes. Thus, Table 1 lists *Specificity* as an “M” for profiles with simulated exposures, even when all other aspects of a study are genuine (e.g., profile 3).

To validly produce evidence of Mechanism, the simulated exposure needs to generate the same outcome with as much fidelity to the actual exposure mechanism as possible. To calculate similarity between the causal pathways for the simulated and actual exposures, we propose another usage of the Hamming distance, which we term the Structural Hamming Distance (SHD). The SHD counts the number of changes required to transform one sub-graph into another through edge additions and deletions. This procedure is shown in Figure 2 and detailed in the steps below.

1. Starting with the DAG for the true exposure, replace the true exposure with the simulated exposure, and add to the DAG any additional nodes needed to complete the exposure-outcome pathway under the simulated exposure.
2. Starting at the exposure node, add any additional arrows required to trace the path of the simulated exposure to the outcome.
3. Starting at the exposure node, delete any arrows coming from the exposure that are not present on the simulated exposure DAG.
4. Count the number of arrow modifications (additions and deletions) made as the structural Hamming distance.

Figure 2. Example of assessing the structural Hamming distance in a simulated exposure. Here the simulated exposure is connected to the outcome through a causal pathway consisting of a set of alternate factors (AF1-AF3), whereas the genuine exposure connects through a set of intermediate factors (IF1-IF3, panel A). In panel B we substitute the simulated exposure for the original and add the variables to the original causal diagram that were unique to the simulated exposure diagram. In panel C we add and delete edges as necessary to transform the causal diagram for the actual exposure into that for the simulated exposure. The sum of the edge deletions and additions is the structural Hamming distance.

The substance of each change is also important. If a key mechanistic node or pathway is omitted with the use of the substitute exposure, then it may be inappropriate to consider it as evidence supporting either *Specificity* or *Mechanism*, even with a low structural Hamming distance. Conversely, if key nodes are replicated in a simulated exposure, a high structural Hamming distance may not be prohibitive to valid translational inference. Here subject matter expertise will be required to adjudicate the importance of structural changes. Finally, it is also important to note that simulated exposures may enter the causal network at an arbitrary location along a known causal pathway. In these cases, it may be appropriate to limit assessment of mechanistic similarity to the subgraph formed by the path traced from the actual exposure to the outcome. However, the causal pathways should be analyzed to ensure that the alternate insertion

point of the simulated exposure does not circumvent important indirect causal pathways to the outcome or create new ones. At the very least, description of known or suspected nodes/pathways and insertion points not accounted for should be included in each description of study limitations.

Proxy Outcomes

Of primary concern for any outcome measure is its validity and reliability. Validity is whether a measure provides information about the outcome in response to the exposure, while reliability is the degree of agreement or consistency (e.g., correlation) between the outcome measure and the actual outcome (12). These properties are represented by the causal pathways in the DAG, and must be demonstrated with empirical evidence. In cases where a proxy outcome is measured instead of the actual outcome of interest, these concerns about reliability and validity are magnified, as the proxy introduces the possibility for differing causal mechanisms, and thus may not have the appropriate relationships required to be a valid proxy. Table 1 reflects this in that almost all profiles with proxy outcomes are prevented from contributing to *Specificity*, and often call *Mechanism* into question as well.

Validity has several subtypes: content validity, criterion validity, and construct validity (12). As content validity is most often concerned with surveys or tests capturing information about a psychological or cognitive domain, and construct validity deals with how proxy measures correlate to each other, for most analog studies criterion validity is most relevant as it describes how predictive a proxy outcome is of the (unmeasured) real outcome variable of interest.

While criterion validity can be demonstrated by empirical data, it is defined by the relationships between the exposure variable, the proxy outcome variable, and the actual outcome variable. In other words, a proxy outcome must have the correct causal relationship to both the exposure and the outcome to be valid. Specifically, the proxy must be a descendant of the exposure, so that the proxy outcome and target outcome co-vary with the exposure as common

cause. Figure 3 shows the relationships that the proxy outcome can have to the exposure and actual outcome: (a) the Proxy is a descendant of the Outcome; (b) the Proxy is an ancestor of the Outcome; or (c) both the Outcome and the Proxy Outcome are independently caused by the Exposure.

Reliability is demonstrated with empirical data, through correlation of the proxy outcome to the actual outcome. In Figure 3A and 3B, reliability will be high when the Exposure variable is a necessary cause of the outcomes, higher still when the Exposure is both a necessary and sufficient cause, and highest when the Exposure is the sole cause. Heuristically, we can intuit that the correlation between the Exposure and any outcomes will be strongest when Exposure is the only cause of the outcomes, and will be diminished when the outcomes have additional, independent causes. In Figure 3C, reliability decreases with the number of edges between exposure and outcome (network distance) on either or both pathways. Conceptually this can be thought of as a “more distant” relationship between the Exposure and either or both of the two outcomes.

Figure 3. Valid proxy outcomes. Scenario A shows the real Outcome as a cause of the Proxy Outcome. Scenario B shows the Proxy Outcome as a cause of the real Outcome. Scenario C shows Exposure as an independent cause of both the Proxy Outcome and the Outcome. All three scenarios create content validity in the Proxy Outcome as both the Outcome and the Proxy Outcome are direct descendants of the exposure.

It is important to note that the proxy and actual outcomes can also be correlated if they both have a common ancestor other than exposure (Figure 4). In such cases the proxy is not valid

because the proxy can be shown to be independent of the exposure through d-separation, meaning variation in the proxy tells us nothing about the effect of exposure on outcome.

Figure 4. An invalid proxy outcome. Conditional on either the Ancestral Factor or the Exposure, Outcome and Proxy Outcome are independent. Stated differently, the Proxy Outcome and Outcome co-vary with the Ancestral Factor rather than with Exposure itself, and any correlation between the Outcome and the Proxy Outcome is spurious.

Examples from Human Spaceflight

Example 1: Urine Chemistry as a Proxy Outcome for Renal Stone Formation

A study by Whitson et al.(13) of renal stone prevention in spaceflight gathered data from 30 human spaceflights on International Space Station (ISS) expeditions and Mir increments. The exposure for ISS crewmembers was potassium citrate or placebo, administered daily, while the Mir cosmonauts acted as additional controls by taking no interventions but still providing urine samples for outcome assessment. The study was interested in drawing inferences about renal stone formation in space, yet the outcomes were proxy outcomes: urine chemistry measures (rather than stone formation itself). Though this study was conducted among humans and in space, this study should be considered an analog owing to the use of a proxy outcome. The analysis of its evidentiary utility therefore centers on the relationship between the proxy outcome and the actual outcome. If the proxy outcome is valid, then this is a Profile 2 analog, and could provide evidence not only toward *Mechanism* but could also contribute toward *Specificity*.

Figure 5 shows a subgraph of the NASA Human System Risk Board’s causal DAG for the renal stone formation risk (14,15). The diagram shows the mechanisms of renal stone formation, including the proposed countermeasure potassium citrate (K+ citrate). The DAG reveals that urine chemistry is a descendent of K+ citrate and an ancestor to the outcome (nephrolithiasis). Since the proxy outcome is a descendent of exposure and an ancestor of the real outcome, it is a valid proxy outcome. (It conforms to the prototype featured in Panel B of Figure 3.) As such, this particular study is able to validly contribute to the evidence for the *Mechanism* of potassium citrate reducing risk of renal stones, as well as the *Specificity* of that mechanism for astronauts in space.

Figure 5. Causal sub-graph for nephrolithiasis, extracted from the NASA “Kidney Stone” risk (14). This graph represents the proxy outcome, Urine Chemistry, as an ancestor of the actual outcome, Nephrolithiasis. Urine concentration is thus a valid proxy outcome for studying nephrolithiasis.

It is worth noting that in the case of human spaceflight risks, nephrolithiasis occurrence is itself actually a proxy outcome for mission level outcomes downstream. It is well known terrestrially that kidney stones can form in the kidney but not cause clinical symptoms because they typically do not enter the ureter.(16) In these cases, if the most appropriate question is about symptomatic nephrolithiasis, then additional steps in the DAG must be added and assessed as above.

Example 2: Cognitive Effects of Space Radiation Using Simulated Exposure Among Mice

A study by Acharya et (17) looked at the cognitive function of mice after chronic exposure to particle radiation at the National Space Radiation Laboratory in Brookhaven, NY.

The research in question caught national attention because of a claim made in the paper, specifically that the number needed to harm (NNH) was between 3.5 and 5.0. Hence the study authors concluded “In a crew of five astronauts traveling to Mars, we would expect at least one member to display severe deficits in each of those cognitive functions by the time they return to Earth(17) Since this research was performed in a terrestrial research laboratory using mice, it qualifies as an analog study.

The *Organism* used for the study was a surrogate, which immediately places the analog in the lower half of Table 1 (profiles 9-16). Here the *Setting* is a substitute, since a terrestrial laboratory was used instead of spaceflight. The *Exposure* too was simulated, using neutron radiation at a low dose rate rather than actual space radiation. (This point deserves special emphasis, since, in addition to the fact that the beam was simulated radiation, its radiation profile is different from the mix of particles that predominates spaceflight exposures.) Finally, the *Outcomes* were proxies of unknown validity: a battery of (rodent) behavioral measures and changes to the hippocampus from radiation damage. Given these substitutions, this study qualifies as analog Profile 16. As such, Table 1 reveals that the results from this can offer us only *Analogy*. Studies such as this can therefore inspire further research by offering an initial signal that neutron radiation may lead to cognitive deficits, but say little about what we should expect from human exposure to space radiation.

Discussion

In this paper we have set forth a system for the evaluation of the translational validity of analog studies through the understanding of which aspects of causality can be satisfied by a given study. This in turn is shown to be dependent on its analog profile. Specifically, we have argued that translational validity is equivalent to evidentiary utility, which is dependent not only on which aspects are substituted, but also on the details of how those factors relate to the actual causal

systems under investigation. When substituted, each of the four aspects of an analog study can create limitations to the utility of information gleaned from an analog study in different ways.

As Table 1 makes clear, the first consideration should be the Organism under study (human or surrogate). After Organism, we believe that the next most important consideration is Setting, which is also the most difficult to assess. From an epistemologically skeptical viewpoint we might therefore conclude that no analog which uses a substitute setting can ever contribute to *Specificity*, and in some cases, this may even give reason to doubt the study's utility in establishing *Mechanism*. However, we feel this is an unnecessarily pessimistic view, as it invites claims regarding a never-ending list of theoretically possible but mechanistically unlikely influences on aggregate system behavior. Not all cases warrant such extreme skepticism, and, since it is not possible to prove a negative, the responsibility lies with the claimant of such influences to provide evidence that their concern has some basis in reality. Nevertheless, scientists should carefully consider possible setting-based confounding before dismissing the use of a substitute *Setting* as inconsequential to the system under study.

A practical consequence of this structure is that satisfying Analogy alone provides minimal evidentiary value. Temporality and Analogy are prerequisites that any non-absurd analog study clears by construction: the exposure must precede the outcome (Temporality), and it must be plausible enough to actually be an analog in some sense (Analogy). Evidence syntheses and risk evaluations should therefore treat both as baseline expectations rather than meaningful contributions; the substantive evidentiary work happens in Mechanism and Specificity, with Consistency and Coherence emerging across studies.

For many of the profiles in Table 1, the ability to contribute to Mechanism and/or Specificity is marked with an "M", meaning that a particular analog study may or may not be able to contribute valid evidence toward that criterion. In these cases, the resolution to this question is entirely dependent on which factor is analog. It is important to note that in the vast majority of such cases, an argument will need to be made to justify one view or the other, and there will be cases where

the wrong decision is made. It is for this reason that the guidelines of Consistency and Coherence are part of Hill's original formulation: the strongest set of evidence for causation would be one where the preponderance of evidence is in agreement.

The requirement of Coherence across studies implies that, by design, we may require a “mosaic” of analog studies to obtain all the needed evidence for establishing the Mechanism and/or Specificity of a hypothesis. In such cases Table 1 could be a guide to which sorts of additional studies may be needed and which would be inadequate to close evidentiary gaps in our knowledge of particular phenomena. Formal causal models provide the common language necessary for assessing translational validity across study types and research groups.

A way to hedge against errors in belief about evidentiary utility is to validate analog platforms or concepts before attempting to use them. Examples of such validation include demonstrating that a particular analog exposure is equivalent in one or more key ways, that the exposure produces either an outcome of interest or a valid proxy, and that the mechanisms are alike in key ways. Such validation studies also afford an excellent opportunity to assess if confounding in substitute settings has been adequately addressed.

While we demonstrated the framework using human spaceflight analogs, the logic applies wherever analog evidence informs inference about a target system. Rodent models in toxicology, psychological paradigms simulating real-world stress, environmental health studies using occupational exposure as proxies for community exposure, and digital twins in engineering all face the same fundamental question: under what conditions does evidence from the analog validly update beliefs about the target?

When used to evaluate existing data, this framework enables scientists and decision-makers to extract maximum value from analog evidence without over-interpreting its reach. When used prospectively during study design, it clarifies the evidentiary limitations inherent in a given analog profile, ensuring that resources are directed toward studies capable of addressing the questions they are designed to answer.

Author Contributions

RJR conceptualized the framework and drafted the manuscript. A.A. and E.L.A. contributed to the manuscript.

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